

**COPING MECHANISMS OF JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL (JHS)
TEACHERS IN FACING CHALLENGES SURROUNDING
CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT, TEACHING STRATEGIES,
AND PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT**

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Abstract:

Coping mechanism proves the condition of professional crisis and identifies teachers a significant reduction and experiences level of orientation in life that leads to the process of reflection and intensification. The study examines the coping mechanisms of the respondents in terms of classroom management, teaching strategies, and professional development. Descriptive quantitative method of research is utilized in the study because it aims systematically and accurately to describe the situation phenomenon and population of the study. The subjects of the study are the Licensed Professional TLE Junior High School Teachers. The study comprised of 22 respondents and is conducted during the academic year 2019-2020. Results show that coping style is commonly thought of the cognitive, affective, and behavioral responses used by an individual to deal with problems encountered in the school and involving students in making decisions about classroom discipline and organizing the class to work out the rules for good behavior in terms of classroom management, effective coping mechanism teaching strategies make the effects of stress less damaging and knowledge that makes a teacher to help students develop in their learning process in terms of teaching strategies, and upgrade knowledge in the teaching profession and what they are expected to teach, knowing the structure, organization and culture of the school helped students feel comfortable in that environment and adapts professional qualities and professional development through training, seminars, and innovations in the teaching profession in terms of professional development.

Keywords: coping mechanism, TLE teachers, challenges face by teachers, classroom management, teaching strategies, and professional development

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1. Introduction

Coping mechanism is one of the most challenging a teacher is facing and a kind of stress where teacher manages in times of difficult situation. How a teacher maintains emotions and well-being in adjusting to a stressful scenario? Creating a pedagogy and psychological support among professional teachers and develops the educational system that provides and addresses problems in their teaching career. Coping mechanism proves the condition of professional crisis and identifies teachers a significant reduction and experiences level of orientation in life that leads to the process of reflection and intensification. It provides a thorough understanding on the significant emotion and essence of professional crisis and identity experiences in support to psychological and professional development among teachers (Sadovnikova, et al., 2018). Hence, it is a stressed occupation among teachers in an educational setting institution where it cannot be escaped (Rao, & Naidu, 2018).

Nevertheless, there are many coping mechanisms in the classroom management because of the behaviors a teacher encounters due to the upbringing and attitude of the students inside the classroom. Student learning measures their cohesiveness and satisfaction in the classroom setting and environment which students feel that they are cared-off in establishing guidelines in the classroom (Barksdale, Peters, & Corrales, 2019). On the other hand, coping mechanism in the classroom affects and predicts stress. It reveals positive skills in learning of the students with passive problem and emotion styles. It helps the teachers to find plans that will enhance students in their learning positive style (Srisongkhram, & Srisongkhram, 2019).

Similarly, to the adoption of the different strategies in teaching because of the many problems a teacher encounters inside the classroom in terms of facilities, teaching and learning aids, resources in teaching, aside from the students. Techniques in teaching and strategies will help them address the situation. Teaching strategies that provide quality of learning among students that must be given emphasis since teachers are the feeders of learning and serves as a source of information. They are a leader, and a manager in the classroom setting. They develop skills and strategy to make learning process an enjoyable one. They also develop interaction and traits toward students. They understand the phenomena in real practice of teaching and acquiring knowledge for proper dissemination of learning. The effectiveness of teaching and learning is based on the needs and interests of the students. Different techniques are being used to encourage and to discover learning. It is an interactive method of teaching to motive learning process for satisfaction on the part of both the teachers and students (Senthamarai, 2018). Furthermore, an effective technique in teaching inside the classroom is a challenge among the teachers. How the objectives and goals are achieved. Mastery of the subject lesson is a matter, but it must be based on the needs of the students to make a success in the teaching strategies. Conveying a lesson efficiently and effectively shapes the learning process of the students (Cohen-Miller, Shamatov, & Merril, 2018).

Additionally, challenges faced by the teachers are their professional development. This is important to them to be upgraded on their knowledge in the field of their profession. The trend at present is the quality of teachers to produce quality of education for a global competency in the world. Professional development describes the intensive evaluative stage ideally on collaborative opportunity in learning. It is where to maintain professionalism in training to be applicable in the choice of work. Embarking on the professional development in the education global world reforms and enhances performance of teachers in school to where they are teaching. The success of the educational systems depends on the professional development provided for their success. Hence, professional development provides the selection of the teacher in effective mechanism in teaching, provides development training process, and provides structure in support to the effective system. Professional development is based on the initiative of the school to where they can provide support for their teachers that will provide greater enhancement for quality teaching. It reinforces the need of the professionals in the promotion of the growth and development of the teachers in excellence and establishing a status on professional teaching in high standards and performance of the teachers (Choy, & Chua, 2019). Lastly, the intervention of the professional development of teachers becomes a support and motivation among them. It is necessary for them to acquire knowledge on their professional career to upgrade the quality of their profession successfully (Cheon, Reeve, Lee, & Lee, 2018).

2. Research Questions

1. What are the coping mechanisms of the respondents in terms of
 - a. classroom management;
 - b. teaching strategies; and
 - c. professional development?
2. Is there a significant correlation on the coping mechanisms of the respondents in terms of classroom management, teaching strategies and professional development?

2.1 Hypothesis

There is no significant correlation on the coping mechanism of the respondents in terms of classroom management, teaching strategies, and professional development.

3. Proposed Innovation, Intention and Strategy

Coping mechanism provides an insight on the academic stress among the teachers in dealing with students. Adjustment to coping mechanism provides a competitive enhancement of teachers in handling untoward behavior to cope with the lesson for the learners (Nagle, & Sharma, 2018).

The proposed innovation, intension and strategies are discussed below:

A. Classroom Management

Classroom management innovation in education approaches will engage students in their learning process. They are being strengthened and equipped with learning process through:

1. Students are given freedom provided that they are guided with the rules and policies in the school for better learning. This means that students are engaged more on focus learning.
2. Approach to learning diverts to classroom management with respect for both the teachers and students. Need to develop values to create learning.
3. Maintain a teacher-student relationship, trust must be given. A better relationship with both the teacher and students will provide a positive result on learning enhancement.
4. Teachers guide students and give possible solutions to issues inside the classroom. A teacher is a facilitator, a leader, and a feeder or learning inside the classroom.

B. Teaching Strategy

Teaching strategy is a tool for teachers to guide their students, plans activity to enhance better learning through:

1. Technology and innovative methods of teaching in the classroom which engage and help students with different stimuli that create learning base activity environment. It provides lesson interesting and fun for the students to learn. Technology provides resources for learning based on the needs of the students looking for efficiency methods in teaching inside the classroom towards the trend of technology in teaching.
2. Cross over in teaching to enrich experiences of students and teachers based on situation for better learning enhancement. It can be through grip session, group discussion, games, field trips and the likes. Educational content can be link to actual experiences of students for discussion.
3. Teaching through flipping classroom. In this technique, the students are made active participants of the learning process by passing the onus of learning on them, it requires the teachers to relegate to the role of resource providers and the students take the responsibility of gathering concepts information. Using various tools of technology, the students are encouraged to constructing knowledge, fill in the information gaps and makes inferences on their own and when needed.
4. Teaching through collaboration as another innovative method of teaching involves encouraging student collaboration for various projects. Teachers can help foster this skill in the classroom by allowing students to learn, to study and to work in groups.

C. Professional Development

Professional development provides teachers to enhance their teaching professions and help them upgrade their knowledge in their chosen career through:

1. Build and design critical thinking, support experimentation and ensure equitable access to teachers through training, seminars, and workshop.
2. Build directly from teachers' professional development plans and allows choice in their professional growth and development.
3. Ensure that teachers have access to technology in and out of the school to equip knowledge in technology as part of their professional development.
4. Provide opportunities to scale-interest driven and innovative practice to every teacher and create more mechanisms for mentoring and teacher to teacher professional development.

3. Research Methods

Descriptive quantitative method of research is utilized in the study because it aims systematically and accurately to describe the phenomenon, situation and population of the study. It answers the what, when, where and how the questions formulated in the study. The research design uses quantitative to manipulate the variables under study. It is the appropriate method in identifying the characteristics, trends, frequencies, categories, and correlations. It understands on how, what, when, or where the study happens. Quantitative descriptive analyses the content key, control, explanation and prediction of the coping mechanism of teachers in terms of classroom management, teaching strategies, and professional development (Riff, Lacy, Fico, & Watson, 2019).

3.1 Participants of the Study

The subjects of the study are the Licensed Professional TLE Teachers in the public secondary school particularly the Junior High School teachers who are handling Technology Livelihood Education (TLE). They are experienced teachers and have the expertise in the coping mechanisms in facing challenges surrounding the classroom management, teaching strategies, and professional development. This is conducted for the period 2019-2020.

3.2 Sources of Data Information

After the approval of the research title by the research committee team in Novaliches High School. The researcher gathered data from the internet, magazines, books, journals, and interview those expert people who have the expertise on coping mechanism of teachers they faced in teaching. All the gathered data are given analysis for the proposal of the research. Survey questionnaire is also formulated for purposes of data gathering of information that can strengthen the background and enhance the study under

investigated. The effectiveness of the information gathered is designed for implementation (Walker, Lee, James, & Ho, 2018).

3.3 Data Analysis

Table 1: Coping mechanism in terms of classroom management

Indicators	WM	Interpretation	Ranking
1. Establish order, engage students, or elicit their cooperation in order to create a classroom environment in which students learn, and teachers manage.	4.09	Very Often	3.5
2. Identify factors preventing from implementing ideas of best classroom management or classroom management in excessive workload, classroom size, layout, and lack of support from the school.	3.38	Sometimes	8
3. Classroom management has been associated with a lower sense of efficacy in determining stress level that consequently, contributes to generating teacher burnout.	4.09	Very Often	3.5
4. Classroom management and coping style is commonly thought of the cognitive, affective, and behavioral responses used by an individual to deal with problems encountered in the school.	4.15	Very Often	1.5
5. Hinting about students' unacceptable behavior without making a demand in describing what students are doing wrong, and expecting them to stop	3.20	Sometimes	9
6. Discussing with students the impact of their behavior has on others, and negotiating with them on a one-to-one basis like getting students to understand why their behavior is a problem.	3.15	Sometimes	10
7. Involving students in making decisions about classroom discipline and organizing the class to work out the rules for good behavior.	4.15	Very Often	1.5
8. Recognizing and rewarding the appropriate behavior of individual students or the class.	4.00	Very Often	6
9. Punishing students who misbehave, increasing the level of punishment if necessary.	4.00	Very Often	6
10. Using aggressive techniques like yelling angrily at students who misbehave.	4.00	Very Often	6
Average Weighted Mean	3.82	Very Often	

Table 1 presents the weighted mean and the corresponding interpretation on the coping mechanism of the respondents in terms of classroom management.

As shown in the table, rank 1 is shared by the two indicators which are “Classroom management and coping style is commonly thought of the cognitive, affective, and behavioral responses used by an individual to deal with problems encountered in the school” and “Involving students in making decisions about classroom discipline and organizing the class to work out the rules for good behavior”, with weighted mean of

4.15 or Very Often. It shows here that classroom management among the teachers is based on the domains of learning so that students are guided properly in their learning enhancement. They are even involved in organizing themselves to become discipline according to the behaviors and rules set by their teachers. Rank 2 is also shared by the two indicators which are “Establish order, engage students, or elicit their cooperation in order to create a classroom environment in which students learn, and teachers manage” and “Classroom management has been associated with a lower sense of efficacy in determining stress level that consequently, contributes to generating teachers’ burnout”, with weighted mean of 4.09 or Very Often. This indicates that classroom is set up before the learning process to become conducive for the learners to study. This can lessen teachers from their stress inside the classroom. Rank 3 is shared by the three indicators which are “Recognizing and rewarding the appropriate behavior of individual students or the class”, “Punishing students who misbehave, increasing the level of punishment if necessary”, and “Using aggressive techniques like yelling angrily at students who misbehave”, with weighted mean of 4.00 or Very Often. This reveals that students are given rewards on their performance and they are being punished for misbehaving to know the values of learning inside the classroom. The least in rank is “Discussing with students the impact of their behavior has on others, and negotiating with them on a one-to-one basis like getting students to understand why their behavior is a problem”, with weighted mean of 3.15 or Sometimes, which means that students are guided properly inside the classroom on the basis of their learning enhancement. The overall average weighted mean is 3.82 which is Very Often to observe in the coping mechanism of the respondents in terms of classroom management.

Table 2: Coping mechanism in terms of teaching strategies

Indicators	WM	Interpretation	Ranking
1. Provides good idea for the most effective way in teaching by providing support to students.	4.20	Always	2
2. Lack of resources or shortage of teaching and learning aids and textbooks.	3.98	Very Often	5
3. Dealing with difficult students, absenteeism, tardiness, and drop-outs due to failure rates.	4.00	Very Often	4
4. Effective coping mechanism teaching strategies make the effects of stress less damaging and knowledge that makes a teacher to help students develop in their learning process.	4.32	Always	1
5. Too many workloads of a teacher that affects the performance in teaching, aside from the class size being handled.	4.13	Very Often	3
Average Weighted Mean	4.12	Very Often	

Table 2 presents the weighted mean and the corresponding interpretation on the coping mechanism of the respondents in terms of teaching strategies.

As noted in the table, it shows that “Effective coping mechanism teaching strategies make the effects of stress less damaging and knowledge that makes a teacher

to help students develop in their learning process”, which is rank 1, with a weighted mean of 4.32 or Always. This indicates that teachers follow the guidelines in the different domains of learning in their teaching strategies to guide students in their learning process. Rank 2 is “Provides good idea for the most effective way in teaching by giving support to students”, with weighted mean of 4.20 or Always. This shows that proper support is given emphasis among the students. Rank 3 is “Too many workloads of a teacher that affects the performance in teaching, aside from the class size being handled”, with weighted mean of 4.13 or Very Often. This indicates that despite of the many workloads of the teachers still they can able to cope with different strategies in teaching that boost the students in their learning process. The least in rank is “Lack of resources or shortages of teaching and learning aids and textbooks”, with weighted mean of 3.98 or Very Often. This is the reason why teaching strategies are important among the respondents. The overall average weighted mean is 4.12 or Very often. This emphasizes that teaching strategies is the best weapon in overcoming coping mechanism among the respondents.

Table 3: Coping mechanism in terms of professional development

Indicators	WM	Interpretation	Ranking
1. Upgrade knowledge in the teaching profession and what they are expected to teach, knowing the structure, organization, and culture of the school helped students feel comfortable in that environment.	4.28	Always	1.5
2. Use of self-management skills such as preparation, planning and organizational skills.	4.10	Very Often	4
3. Adapts professional qualities and professional development through training, seminars, and innovations in the teaching profession.	4.28	Always	1.5
4. Promote a growth mindset, professional development opportunities to boost students’ outcome.	4.18	Very Often	3
5. Create opportunities for teachers to deepen their understanding for effective teacher professional development.	3.95	Very Often	5
Average Weighted Mean	4.15	Very Often	

Table 3 presents the weighted mean and the corresponding interpretation on the coping mechanism of the respondents in terms of professional development.

As seen in the table, rank 1 is shared by the two indicators which are “Upgrade knowledge in the teaching profession and what they are expected to teach, knowing the structure, organization, and culture of the school helped students feel comfortable in that environment”, and “Adapts professional qualities and professional development through training, seminars, and innovations in the teaching profession”, with weighted mean of 4.28 or Always. This indicates that teachers are trained in their profession of career through in service training, and other professional development to upgrade their knowledge in their teaching profession. Rank 2 is “Promote a growth mindset,

professional development opportunities to boost students' outcome", with weighted mean of 4.18 or Very Often. This shows that professional development among the respondents can help improve knowledge of the students. Rank 3 is "Use of self-management skills such as preparation, planning, and organizational skills", with weighted mean of 4.10 or Very Often. This shows that professional development among the respondents prepare them to organize and to plan their skills in molding and shaping students in their chosen career. The least in rank is "Create opportunities for teachers to deepen their understanding for effective teacher professional development", with weighted mean of 3.95 or Very Often. This provides teachers the opportunity to develop their professional growth in the teaching professions. The overall average weighted mean is 4.15 or Very Often. This is the reason why teachers need to enhance their professional growth and development to upgrade their knowledge in their chosen career.

Table 4: Significant correlation on the coping mechanisms of the respondents in terms of classroom management, teaching strategies and professional development

Variable	Computed r-value	Relationships *significant *not significant	Hypotheses *accepted *rejected
1. Classroom Management vs. Teaching Strategies	0.0537	Not Significant	Accepted
2. Classroom vs. Professional Development	0.0535	Not Significant	Accepted
3. Teaching Strategies vs. Professional Development	0.0515	Not Significant	Accepted

Significant at 0.05 level, one-tailed test, df at 20 with critical r-value of 0.423

Table 4 shows the significant correlation on the coping mechanisms of the respondents in terms of classroom management, teaching strategies, and professional development. It reveals in the table that when the variables are tested against each variables, the result shows that all the computed r value is lower than a critical r value of 0.423 which means the relationship is not significant. Therefore, the hypothesis is accepted while the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that there is no significant correlation on the coping mechanisms of the respondents in terms of classroom management, in terms of teaching strategies, and in terms of professional development.

3.4 Work Plan and Timeliness

A. Classroom Management

Classroom management must be designed according to the needs of the students and coping style must also be based on the different domains of learning in the cognitive, affective, and behavioral responses used by an individual to deal with problems encountered in the school classroom. This can involve students in making decision about

classroom discipline and organizing the class to work out the rules for good behavior. The outcome of the academic performance of the students is based on the classroom management set-up for conducive learning. Consider the ability of the students especially on their behavior to their study habits. The competency in the academic performance of the students demonstrates the control in the classroom on the measurement of their output to learning process (Reinke, Herman, & Dong, 2018).

B. Teaching Strategies

Provide an effective coping mechanism teaching strategies that make the effects of stress less damaging and knowledge that makes a teacher to help students develop their learning process. Plan for the effective teaching strategies base on the needs and behaviors of the students because this can help in the coping mechanism of the respondents and to understand that teaching incorporates values and makes sense of responsibility in carrying the objectives of the lesson. Evaluation in the teaching strategies is based on the outcome and result of the learning performance of the students (Harris, 2019).

C. Professional Development

Upgrade professional knowledge among the teachers because they are expected to teach, knowing the structure, organization and culture of the school that can help students feel comfortable in the environment of learning. They can also adapt professional qualities and professional development through training, seminars, and innovations in the teaching profession. It examines the teacher's characteristics on their development of professional program in support to the design and application of their teaching career to include active learning, closely related to existing teaching collective participation sufficient for their professional development and growth. It facilitates change among the teachers to be successful in their career as teacher professionals (Valiandes, & Neophytou, 2018).

3.5 Plans for Dissemination and Utilization

A. Classroom Management

Teachers should orient students on the classroom behavior at the start of the classes in the academic year for them to be guided in their learning process inside the classroom. Consider the different attitude of the students that comes from different characteristics of the family to where they adopt in life. Value inculcation must be the priority of the teacher in the classroom management. When there is a proper classroom management, they can see the result of the learning output of the students in their academic performance. Behavior problems can be address and there is a smooth classroom discussion inside the classroom.

B. Teaching Strategies

There is a need to design a different teaching strategy among the students because of the lack of resources or shortage of teaching and learning aids and textbooks which affect the learning output of the students. Proper teaching strategies enhance learning ability of the students. This includes techniques in the delivery of the lesson plans based on their needs. Consider the individual differences of the students. There are two kinds of learners, the slow learners and the fast learners in which teaching strategies are based on their knowledge of learning.

C. Professional Development

There is a need to upgrade knowledge of teachers. This can be done through undergoing a professional growth and development. This is not limited to in services training but can be also extended to the knowledge needed by the teachers in their professional development. With the trends of technology now, everything is upgraded to be globally competent as teachers in the academe. Create opportunities for teachers to deepen their understanding for effective teacher professional development. This can be done through seminars and workshop on the different trends of professional development among them.

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